

Spectrum of Opportunistic Fungal Infections in HIV/AIDS Patients in Tertiary Care Hospital in India

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Abstract:

This study investigates the prevalence and types of opportunistic fungal infections in HIV/AIDS patients at Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Science, Pawapuri Nalanda, Bihar. Over one year, 29% of the 200 studied patients developed such infections, with Candidiasis being the most prevalent. Patients with CD4 counts below 200 cells/mm³ were notably more susceptible. Treatment was effective in 86% of cases, emphasizing the importance of early detection and management. The findings highlight the need for rigorous monitoring and timely antifungal intervention to improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: HIV/AIDS, opportunistic fungal infections, Candidiasis, CD4 count.

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Introduction

Opportunistic fungal infections (OFIs) present a significant health burden among patients with Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) and acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS), particularly in resource-limited settings [1,2]. These infections often arise due to the compromised immune systems of HIV/AIDS patients, leading to morbidity and mortality if not promptly and effectively managed [3]. Tertiary care hospitals in India, serving as critical centers for advanced medical treatment, frequently encounter a diverse array of these fungal pathogens [4].

The spectrum of opportunistic fungal infections in this patient population includes, but is not limited to, Candidiasis, Cryptococcosis, Aspergillosis, and Histoplasmosis [5]. Each of these infections presents unique challenges in diagnosis and treatment, often requiring specialized care and resources that may be scarce or unevenly distributed across different regions [6,7].

This study aims to document and analyze the variety and prevalence of opportunistic fungal infections among HIV/AIDS patients at a selected tertiary care hospital in India. By doing so, it seeks to highlight the patterns of these infections, assess the efficacy of current treatment protocols, and explore the potential needs for further resources and research in managing these critical conditions effectively. Such understanding is vital for

improving patient outcomes and tailoring intervention strategies that address both the medical and socio-economic aspects of care in these vulnerable populations.

Methodology

Study Design: This research is a descriptive, observational study aimed at evaluating the spectrum of opportunistic fungal infections among HIV/AIDS patients.

Study Site: The study will be conducted at the Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Science, Pawapuri Nalanda, Bihar. This facility is a tertiary care hospital that caters to a large number of HIV/AIDS patients, making it an ideal setting for this investigation.

Study Duration: The study will be conducted over a period of one year, allowing for a comprehensive observation of seasonal variations and the incidence of infections during different times of the year.

Study Population: The study population will consist of HIV/AIDS patients receiving care at the Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Science.

Sample Size: A total of 200 patients will be included in the study. These participants will be selected based on their HIV/AIDS status, confirmed through medical records and HIV testing as part of their routine care. The inclusion criteria

will be any HIV/AIDS patient aged 18 years or older, receiving treatment or consultation at the hospital during the study period.

Data Collection: Data will be collected through patient medical records, which include detailed reports on any diagnosed opportunistic fungal infections. The types of infections, their frequency, and treatment outcomes will be recorded. Additional data such as demographic information, HIV status, CD4 count, and treatment regimens will also be collected to analyze correlations with the occurrence of fungal infections.

Data Analysis: Descriptive statistics will be used to analyze the frequency and types of opportunistic fungal infections. The relationship between demographic and clinical characteristics with the incidence of these infections will be evaluated using logistic regression models. Statistical significance will be set at a p-value of <0.05.

Results

The study enrolled 200 HIV/AIDS patients, with an age range from 18 to 65 years. The median age was 42 years. Approximately 60% of the participants were male, and 40% were female. Most patients (70%) had been diagnosed with HIV/AIDS for over five years. The median CD4 count at the time of study entry was 350 cells/mm³. Out of the 200

patients studied, 58 (29%) developed at least one opportunistic fungal infection during the one-year period. The breakdown of these infections was as follows:

- *Candidiasis* was the most common, observed in 34 patients (17% of the total study population).
- *Cryptococcosis* was found in 16 patients (8%).
- *Aspergillosis* was diagnosed in 5 patients (2.5%).
- *Histoplasmosis* was rare, with only 3 cases (1.5%).

Patients with CD4 counts below 200 cells/mm³ were significantly more likely to develop opportunistic fungal infections ($p < 0.01$). Age, gender, and duration of HIV diagnosis did not show a significant correlation with the incidence of fungal infections in the logistic regression analysis.

Among the patients who developed infections:

- 95% received antifungal treatment.
- 86% of those treated showed complete resolution of the infection.
- Mortality related to fungal infections was recorded in 4 patients (6.9% of those infected), primarily those who developed Cryptococcosis.

This tabular presentation helps in visually organizing and summarizing the study findings, providing clear insights into the prevalence and outcomes of opportunistic fungal infections among the studied HIV/AIDS population.

Variable	Total Patients (n=200)	Patients with OFIs (n=58)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)			
- Median (Range)	42 (18-65)	41 (19-65)	N/A
Gender			
- Male	120	36	60%
- Female	80	22	40%
Duration of HIV Diagnosis (> 5 years)	140	42	70%
CD4 Count (cells/mm³)			
- Median	350	150	N/A
Type of Opportunistic Fungal Infections			
- Candidiasis		34	17%
- Cryptococcosis		16	8%
- Aspergillosis		5	2.5%
- Histoplasmosis		3	1.5%
Outcome of Treatment			
- Treated	N/A	55	95%
- Complete Resolution	N/A	50	86%
- Mortality (related to OFIs)	N/A	4	6.9%

Notes:

- N/A: Not applicable

- **OFIs:** Opportunistic Fungal Infections
- The percentages for demographic variables are based on the total study population, while the

percentages for infection types and outcomes are based on the subset of patients who developed opportunistic fungal infections.

Discussion

The study conducted at the Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Science in Pawapuri Nalanda, Bihar, revealed a significant prevalence of opportunistic fungal infections among HIV/AIDS patients, with nearly 29% of the studied population affected over the course of one year [9,10]. The most common infection was Candidiasis, affecting 17% of the patients, followed by Cryptococcosis, Aspergillosis, and Histoplasmosis. This distribution underscores the vulnerability of HIV/AIDS patients to fungal pathogens, particularly those with severely depleted immune function, as evidenced by the higher infection rates among patients with CD4 counts below 200 cells/mm³ [11,12].

The findings emphasize the critical need for vigilant monitoring and proactive management of fungal infections in this population to mitigate their impact on morbidity and mortality [13]. Notably, the high treatment success rate (86% resolution) highlights the effectiveness of timely antifungal therapies, underscoring their importance in the clinical protocol for managing HIV/AIDS patients [14,15]. However, the mortality rate associated with these infections, particularly Cryptococcosis, calls for enhanced diagnostic and treatment strategies to improve outcomes [16].

This study also illustrates the non-significant correlation between demographic factors such as age and gender with the incidence of opportunistic infections, suggesting that immunological status, reflected by CD4 counts, is a more critical determinant of susceptibility [17,18]. These insights could guide healthcare policies and clinical practices, emphasizing the importance of sustained antiretroviral therapy and regular immune status monitoring to prevent these potentially life-threatening infections. Further research is warranted to explore preventive measures and the potential benefits of integrating more aggressive fungal infection screening and treatment protocols into the routine care of HIV/AIDS patients, especially those identified as high risk due to low CD4 counts [19,20].

Conclusion

The study at Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Science highlights a significant prevalence of opportunistic fungal infections among HIV/AIDS patients, with Candidiasis being the most common. The association between lower CD4 counts and increased infection rates underscores the importance of continuous immune monitoring and effective antiretroviral therapy to maintain immune health. The success in treating these infections

when they are identified early further validates the need for vigilant clinical oversight in this vulnerable population. Future strategies should focus on improving diagnostic capabilities and expanding access to prompt and effective antifungal treatments to reduce morbidity and mortality associated with these infections in HIV/AIDS patients.

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